

Spotlight: Ocean mesoscale

Version V1
September 2025

Background

The study of ocean mesoscale dynamics is key to improving climate understanding and prediction. Mesoscale features such as eddies, fronts, and filaments, occurring on scales of 10–500 km and days to months, transport heat, carbon, oxygen, and nutrients, modulate air–sea interactions, and influence major circulation patterns like the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation. These processes also shape ecosystem variability and primary productivity, with implications for fisheries and marine resources. To characterize them, Essential Ocean Variables such as sea surface height, currents, temperature, and chlorophyll are monitored using satellite observations and in situ platforms including Argo floats, gliders, and moorings. New observing technologies, such as the SWOT satellite mission, provide unprecedented resolution to close existing gaps and better capture mesoscale and submesoscale dynamics.

The Challenge

Mesoscale features are challenging to represent in global climate models: they are too small to be fully resolved, yet too large to ignore, as they can significantly affect ocean transport, heat redistribution, and climate predictions. Accurately observing and modeling these processes requires combining satellite observations, in situ measurements, and high-resolution modeling approaches.

ObsSea4Clim activities

Mesoscale activity varies strongly across the global ocean, with regional differences in intensity, dynamics, and impacts on climate and ecosystems. To capture this diversity, ObsSea4Clim focuses on different regions where mesoscale processes play a key role in regulating circulation, biogeochemical fluxes, and marine productivity.

- In the Mediterranean Sea, work focuses on reviewing different satellite altimetry data sets to better observe spatio-temporal variability of mesoscale features and describe mesoscale indicators (Eddy Kinetic Energy, eddies characteristics). In parallel, in situ data from the Spanish-funded Fast-SWOT project are used to assess the improvements brought by the SWOT mission, launched in December 2022.
- In the Labrador and Irminger Seas, research examines how mesoscale and submesoscale processes modulate lateral and vertical fluxes of tracers such as heat, oxygen and nutrients. In June-July 2024, a selected eddy was identified, and an in situ adaptive sampling strategy was applied to investigate its physical-biogeochemical 3D properties, as well as its surrounding submesoscale structures.

**Funded by
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- In the Central and European Arctic Corridor (e.g., Lofoten Basin), we focus on developing a satellite sensor synergy approach to identify mesoscale eddies together with SWOT's Karin data. Mesoscale activity in this region plays a central role in poleward heat and salt transport and regulates primary productivity in polar waters.
- In the Northwest Atlantic and southwest of Africa, we collaborate through the EUREC4A-OA and WHIRLS projects. Both focus on investigating the impact of fine-scale processes on climate and marine biogeochemistry. A key outcome of this work is the development of the global eddy atlas TOEddies, which explicitly accounts for eddy merging and splitting events. The projects also examine the physical mechanisms underlying the coherence—and remarkably long lifetimes—of mesoscale eddies, as well as their role in the Lagrangian transport of ocean properties.

Resources

1. Presentation on **satellite altimetry revealing intensification of Eddy Kinetic Energy** in the Mediterranean Sea, delivered by Paul Hargous (IMEDEA-CSIC) at European Geosciences Union (EGU) General Assembly 2025.
Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/15533766>
2. **Codes for analysis** used in a paper by Barceló-Llull B. (CSIC) et al.: Kuroshio Extension and Gulf Stream dominate the Eddy Kinetic Energy intensification observed in the global ocean.
Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15655616>
3. Poster on **Eddy Kinetic Energy intensification in the Mediterranean Sea** from three decades of satellite altimetry observations, delivered by Paul Hargous (IMEDEA-CSIC) at Living Planet Symposium 2025.
Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/17084961>
4. Presentation on **intensification of global ocean Eddy Kinetic Energy** based on three decades of satellite altimetry observations, delivered by Bàrbara Barceló-Llull (IMEDEA-CSIC) at The Physical Oceanography Encounter 2024 (EOF 2024).
Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/17092293>
5. Presentation on **global trends in Eddy Kinetic Energy** over the altimetric era delivered by Bàrbara Barceló-Llull (IMEDEA-CSIC) at the "30 Years of progress in radar altimetry" symposium.
Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/17092355>

Latest Publications

1. Barceló-Llull, B., Rosselló, P., Combes, V., *et al.* (2025). Kuroshio Extension and Gulf Stream dominate the Eddy Kinetic Energy intensification observed in the global ocean. *Scientific Reports*, Vol. 15, 21754.
<https://zenodo.org/records/16088545>

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